
WORKLOAD AND REMUNERATIONS AS CORRELATES OF TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated workload and remunerations as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 5,412 respondents (263 principals and 5,149 teachers) of 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 803 respondents (263 principals and 540 teachers) drawn using stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Two sets of instruments titled "Workload and Remunerations Questionnaire (WRQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ)" were used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The construct validation of the instruments was determined using factor analysis. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistency of the instrument which yielded coefficients of 0.79 for WRQ and 0.85 for TJCQ. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is a negligible positive and significant relationship between workload and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Also, there is a negligible positive and significant relationship between remunerations and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that teachers should be rewarded with cash, materials and equipment which boost up the teachers' work motivation and enhance their commitment to the school work.

Keywords: Workload, Remunerations, Teachers, Job Commitment, Schools

Introduction

Education is an indispensable tool for developing the attitudes, skills and knowledge of individuals to enable them make positive contribution to social, economic and political changes in the society. It is also a means of shaping the habit and character of individuals to make them responsible members of the society. Ibezim (2024) noted that education is a potent tool for equipping individuals with skills and sound knowledge for self-reliance and useful contributions towards the affairs of the society. The success of educational system of any country to a large extent depends on the job commitment of teachers.

Teachers' job commitment is the attachment and dedication of teaching staff towards their duties. Ibezim (2024) asserted that teachers' job commitment is dedication and willingness of members of teaching staff to invest their time efforts and time in discharging their duties in secondary schools. In the view of Okeke-James, Igbokwe, Onyilibe and Mokwe (2023), teachers' job commitment is the ability of academic staff to focus, sincere and dedicated in undertaking teaching responsibility. Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) noted that teachers' job commitment is the work attitude and behaviour exhibited by teaching staff towards attainment of predetermined educational goals and objectives. Continuing, the authors stressed that teachers who are committed to their job are punctual to work, deliver instruction at the stipulated period, cover scheme of work and participate in school functions. Teachers who are committed to their job have high zeal to effectively carry out their duties in secondary schools. Teachers' job commitment is defined by Nwokolo and Ajufo (2024) as the act identification, involvement and loyalty to activities carried out in the school environment.

Teachers with high level of commitment are regular in school, arrive early to work, teach with up-dated lesson notes and dedicated in teaching the students. In contrast, teachers with low level of commitment are irregular in school, arrive late to work, teach with out-dated lesson notes and undedicated in teaching the students. Ikedimma and Okorji (2023) noted that the job commitment of teachers is below expectation as evidenced from their absenteeism, low turnover in work place, lateness to class and ineffectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. In the same vein, Ibezim (2024) observed that some teachers exhibit undesirable organization behaviours such as frequent absenteeism, disengagement from official duties, departure from school before the closing hour and procrastination in teaching students which may indicate laxities in their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Teachers are likely exhibit low commitment to their job, when their workload is high.

Workload is generally defined as the extent of the processing capacity that is expended during the performance of a task and thus involves the interaction between resource supply and task demand. Workload is determined by the relationship between task demands, the circumstances under which that task takes place and the perceptions, actions, skills and knowledge of the individual performing the task (Rahman & Avan, 2016). The task demands may include physical actions, cognitive tasks and/or a variety of other factors. These definitions suggested that workload is concerned with the relationship between the task demand and the person's resources, which include skills, knowledge, behaviour and task perception (Basarudin et al., 2016) Workload can also be defined as the expenditure incurred by a person, given their capacities (resources), while achieving a particular level of performance on a particular task with certain demands. The workload is the all-encompassing and wide-ranging activity that consumes teachers' time. This includes but not limited to executing professional duties and responsibilities,

as well as the direct/indirect pursuit of work-related interests. Rahman and Avan (2016) defined teachers' specific workload as the amount of time spent in performing a portfolio of researching and teaching tasks, facilitating co-curricular activities, and being involved in meetings, among others. The workloads of academics are grouped into at least five categories which are teaching and supervision, publication, research and consultation, managerial work, and community services (Basarudin et al., 2016). As commonly reported, when subjected to greater job demand of tasks, the common manifestation is numerous errors and delayed responses. Additionally, two causes of diminishing performance quality are high-task workload and task complexity. Sufficient studies have found that work overload is a stress trigger when employees are confronted with either the quantity or difficulty of tasks (Kimura et al., 2018). As the task quantity/volume and difficulty increases, employees' level of job stress rises in tandem. Finally, many studies have examined the workload-job/ stress-job performance dynamics (Pace et al., 2019).

The use of remuneration in return for educators in the organization as well as being a form of independence is also the responsibility of the leadership in improving job commitment. Remuneration covers how people are rewarded in accordance with their value to the organization (Vito, 2017). It is about both financial and non-financial rewards and embraces the strategies, policies, structure and processes used to develop and maintain the reward system. Effective remuneration practices can be seen as means to meet organizational objectives, such as increasing morale and retaining and attracting good teachers. The evolvement of remuneration arrangement reflects the drive of management to strong corporate performance. Performance cannot be achieved optimally if remuneration is not given proportionally. Remuneration is a compensation paid to an employee by the employer in exchange for services rendered. Regarding an organization, Vito (2017) described remuneration as the pay a person receives in exchange for the work he /she does for the organization. Hence no organization can function well and achieve its goals without adequate remuneration for its employees. Adequate remuneration in teaching profession enable teachers in the satisfaction of their needs, increases job satisfaction and maintains high commitment in teaching. Remuneration can be provided in the form of overtime pay, housing allowance, transport allowance, pension scheme, health scheme, incentives, among others.

Roles and duties assigned to teachers appear to be high in public secondary schools in Anambra State. There are teachers who are assigned two or more subjects for different classes to teach on a daily basis in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The high workload of teachers tends to put them into stress and pressure in secondary schools in Anambra State. The remuneration of teachers tends to be meagre in secondary schools. Obikwelu and Nwasor (2021) asserted that secondary school teachers also complained that their respective individual inputs were not commensurate to the income they received. This could reduce the morale of teachers in discharging their job in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is in the light of this problem that the study investigated workload and remunerations as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine workload and remunerations as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Verify the extent of relationship between workload and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Examine the extent of relationship between remunerations and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of the relationship between workload and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent of the relationship between remuneration and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between workload and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between remuneration and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Anambra State located in South East, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 5,412 respondents (263 principals and 5,149 teachers) of 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 803 respondents (263 principals and 540 teachers) drawn using stratified and simple random sampling techniques.

Two sets of instruments titled "Workload and Remunerations Questionnaire (WRQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ)" were used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The construct validation of the instruments was determined using factor analysis. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistency of the instrument which yielded coefficients of 0.79 for WRQ and 0.85 for TJCQ. All the items of the two instruments are structured on a four point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instruments were administered by the researcher and five research assistants. A total of 803 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 736 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 91 percent return rate. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was

used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. The research questions was interpreted using the coefficient r and the size of the relationship recommended by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05 the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis on the extent of relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		Workload	Teachers job commitment	Remark
Workload	Pearson Correlation	1	0.09	Negligible positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.09	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient from the Table 1 above showed a negligible positive relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, with ‘r’ = 0.09** and N =736. This revealed value of 0 .09 indicated that there is a negligible positive relationship existing between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in

Research Question 2: What is the extent of relationship between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis on the extent of relationship between Remunerations and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

		Correlations		Teachers job commitment	Remark
Remuneration	Pearson Correlation	1	0.06**		Negligible positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00		
	N	736	736		
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.06**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00			
	N	736	736		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient from the Table 2 above showed a negligible positive relationship between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, with ‘r’ = 0.06** and N =736. This revealed positive correlation coefficient value of 0.06 indicated that there is a negligible positive relationship existing between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		Teachers job commitment	Decision
Workload	Pearson Correlation	1	0.09**		Significant relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00		
	N	736	736		
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.09**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00			
	N	736	736		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 3 above showed a significant relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State with r = -0.09..n =736 and p-

value =0.00 . Since p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Table 4: Test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		Remuneration	Teachers job commitment	Decision
Remuneration	Pearson Correlation	1	0.06**	significant relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.06**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	736	736	

The result of the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 4 above showed a significant relationship between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.06^{**}$ $n = 736$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.000$. Since p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between remuneration and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that negligible positive and significant relationship between workload and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools. This result was attributed to the findings that principals and teachers agreed to the fact that every teacher is treated equitably in distribution of course allocation, staff strength is balanced in equitable distribution of workload in school, having large classes increases teachers’ workload demands, excessive workload of teachers leads to anxiety, high level of infrastructure leads to fast delivery of teachers workload, excessive workload of teachers’ leads to frustration, moderate workload helps teachers’ accomplish responsibilities within a given time, teachers’ excessive workload affect efficiency, frequent changes in school policies influence teachers workload. This finding is in disagreement to the findings of Ayeni and Amanekwe (2018) that examined teachers’ workload and determined its implication on students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Akoko North East Local Government Area of Ondo State. The findings indicated that teachers’ workload is high in teaching activities (75.8%), data imputation (62.5%), and marking of students’ scripts (76.7%), and that it impacted negatively on teachers’ instructional tasks performance and students’ academic performance.

The finding of the study indicated that there existed a negligible positive and significant relationship between remunerations and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. This findings is as a result of teachers' and principals agreeing that their salary takes care of their needs, sufficient income helps them to live well, remuneration provides financial security for teachers, teachers are well paid compared with other civil servants, teachers' salary is promptly paid, teachers receive their allowances, teachers are well paid in proportion to their duties, teachers receive the approved minimum wage, teachers' income is adequate for normal expenses, teachers' receive necessary fringe benefits. Result from that study showed that remuneration boost high commitment, especially when basic pay is high and there is bonuses and allowances. This is in line with the findings of Dinensio *et.al* (2021) that investigated the relationship between remuneration and job performance of teachers in government-aided secondary schools in Western Uganda and whose findings revealed that job performance of teachers. Also in consonance with Ogonda, *et.al* (2015) who studied the relationship between Remuneration and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Rarieda Sub-County, Kenya. Their findings showed that there was a positive influence of remuneration on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Rarieda Sub-County, Kenya. There was a significant relationship between remuneration and teachers' job satisfaction.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that workload and remuneration have negligible positive and significant relationship with teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Fair workload reduces job stress and good remuneration enable teachers to satisfy their needs which motivate them to exhibit high job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of this study:

1. Principals should ensure that teachers' workloads are moderate to avoid poor performance of teachers in schools.
2. Teachers should be rewarded with cash, materials and equipment which boost up the teachers' work motivation and enhance their commitment to the school work.

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